

ISic0350

Epitaph for Cnaeus Fabius Titianus

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Found during excavation of the foundations for the new church of S.
Caterina di Siena of the Dominican friars in 1731 (so Amico)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 504

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Cn (aeus) Fabius Fe [lix] [pat (er)]
2. Antonia Sym [pheru] sa mat (er) Cn (aeo) Fa [bio Ti] tiano f (ilio) vix (it)
an [n (is) ---]

Apparatus

Text of Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Cnaeus Fabius Felix, the father, and Antonia Sympherusa, the mother, (made
this) for Cnaeus Fabius

Titianus, their son, who lived [---] years [---].

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491559

EDR 139218
EDCS 21900388

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7066 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 86

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